

On behalf of the Scientific Committee, I'm pleased to welcome you at the Third International Scientific Conference Dentistry 2018 Novi Sad "Contemporary concepts of endodontics-In Memoriam prof. dr Tatjana Brkanić and orthodontics therapy" and "Contemporary concept of dentoalveolar rehabilitation".

The Scientific and Organization Committee have made every effort to plan a conference that is scientifically satisfactory and socially interesting.

You will meet with an exceptional program covering different topics, from basic research areas to areas within daily practice of Restorative Dentistry, Endodontics, Prosthodontics, Oral Surgery and Implantology, Periodontology, Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry. Technical and Dental Material exhibits will also form an important segment of the Conference.

Apart from the scientific aspect of the Conference we wish you to experience the traditional hospitality of Novi Sad and to strengthen the existing friendships and create a lot of new ones.

*President of the Scientific Committee
Doc. dr Aleksandra Maletin*

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07.06.2018.

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NONSURGICAL TREATMENT OF EXTENSIVE PERIAPICAL LESION DUE TO TRAUMA

Bojana Ramić¹, Milica Cvjetičanin¹, Karolina Vukoje¹, Ivana Kantardžić¹, Milan Drobac², Igor Stojanac², Ljubomir Petrović²

¹ Department of Dentistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

² Department of Dentistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Dental Clinic of Vojvodina
Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to show a clinical case of a single-root, intact tooth with pulp necrosis and a large periapical lesion which reached full recovery after being non-surgically, endodontically treated with calcium-hydroxide in combination with iodoform. Traumatic injuries of teeth have frequent occurrence and usually involve maxillary incisors in young patients. Pulpal necrosis and later bacterial contamination of root canal system usually happen after traumatic injury of the tooth. As a consequence of bacteria colonizing, host-defense system develops chronic inflammation and bone resorption in periradicular tissues. The patient is usually without any symptom, until the equilibrium between host and bacteria isn't damaged, when starts intense pain to chewing and/or swelling. Treatment options to manage large periapical lesions are non-surgical endodontic treatment and apical surgery. Proper mechanical preparation and debridement of root canal along with copious irrigation with NaOCl contributes to elimination of huge number of bacteria. Additional treatment includes root canal medication based on calcium-hydroxide which can be combined with iodoform in order to expand antibacterial spectrum that is mainly effective against remaining bacteria. After withdrawal of all patient's symptoms, root canal should be three-dimensional obturated and coronal restoration should be placed as soon as it is possible to prevent microleakage. After 6 months, if the patient is out of symptoms, control radiograph should be taken to assess prognosis of treated tooth. In healthy, especially younger patients, first signs of healing periapical tissue could be detected in examined radiograph as a density changes within the lesion.